

PHILOLOGY

SPECIFIC PECULIARITIES OF THE AZERBAIJANI LANGUAGE IN THE ISTANBUL COPY OF IBN MUHANNA'S DICTIONARY

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Abstract

The article examines and compares part of the Turkic language of the European and Istanbul manuscripts of Jamal al-Din Ibn al-Muhanna's dictionary "Kitab hilyatul-insan wa halbatul-lisan" (كتاب حلية الإنسان و حلية اللسان). All researchers accept unanimously P.M.Melioransky's scientific results about the fact that parts of the Turkic language in all five European manuscripts belong to the medieval Azerbaijani language. But scientists' opinions about the Istanbul manuscript do not coincide.

The article deals with the positions of scientists such as S.Malov, A.Erjilasun, A.Battal, B.Chobanzadeh and systematizes the following linguistic facts specific to Azerbaijani Turkic language based on the latest version of Ibn Muhanna's dictionary: 1) the lengthening of vowels at the end of Turkic words (قَلِيح، كِشِي، قَرْنَتاش) in the Arabic alphabet indicates that the stress falls on the last syllable of the word; 2) words ending with voiced consonants; 3) the consonant *q* (ق) in the middle of the word in other Turkic dialects is widely changed to *x* (خ) in Azerbaijani Turkic; 4) according to Melioransky, the formation of the auxiliary verb *ol-maq* (trans.: to be) as a result of the dropping the *b* sound from the root of the word *bulmak* is a specific peculiarity only for Southern Turkic dialects; 5) the transition *ç > ş* ([ch]>[sh]), *c > ş* ([j]>[sh]) is a characteristic feature of Azerbaijani dialects; 6) dropping of consonant *y* at the beginning of words; 7) the presence of the suffix *-durur*.

Keywords: Ibn Muhanna's dictionary, "Kitab hilyatul-insan wa halbatul-lisan", Turkestan Turkic, Chagatai, Uyghur, suffix.

Introduction

Six copies of Jamal al-Din Ibn al-Muhanna's dictionary "Kitab hilyatul-insan wa halbatul-lisan" (كتاب حلية الإنسان و حلية اللسان), which was written in the style of learner's dictionary of Arabic lexicography in the 13th century, are known until now. The last one is preserved in the Archaeological Museum Library (Arkeoloji Müzesi Kütüphanesi, no. 1202) in Istanbul, and the date of its copy is attributed to the 16th century. Finally, according to this manuscript, it became known to the world of science that the author of the dictionary "Hilyatul-insan ve halbatul-lisan" is Jamal al-Din Ibn al-Muhanna.

Main body

"Turkestan Turkic" and "our country's Turkic" (Azerbaijani Turkic) are compared in the same way [See: 18, pp. 79-80; 13, p. 09], even differences such as suffixes and sound changes are shown in European and Istanbul copies of the work, which was written in the state of Ilkhanate. Bekir Chobanzadeh shows that comparisons are made at 72 times on pages 78-90 of the Istanbul copy [4, p. 59]. Examples of these comparisons include:

In Turkestan Turkic	Azerbaijani Turkic	Meaning
İdi (ايدى), iži (ايذى)	İti (ايتى)	Owner
ətkü (اتكو), əžkü (اژكو)	Eykü (ايكو)	Good
ədaq (اداق), əžaq (اژاق)	Ayaq (اياق)	Foot, glass

Special attention that was paid to the Turkestan dialect in Ibn Muhanna's dictionary shows the influence of the speakers of this language at that time.

Sergey Malov considers that association of the European copies with the Azerbaijani language by Melioransky, who was his teacher, is justified. However, he suggests that the Istanbul copy is in Uyghur. Bekir Chobanzadeh, who proved on scientific grounds that Azerbaijani Turkic language is reflected in the abovementioned dictionary, disagreed with Malov's opinion and had a scientific debate with him personally, as a result of this debate, he got Professor Sergey Yefimovich's support [4, p. 97].

Abdullah Battal, repeating Malov's opinion, expresses his certainty that the European copies of Ibn

Muhanna's dictionary correspond to the ancient Azerbaijani language, but the Istanbul copy is in Eastern Turkic, Kashgar and Uyghur languages [2, p. 2]. Ahmet B. Ercilasun, besides titling the work as "Hilyetü'l-Lisân ve Hulbetü'l-Beyân", refers the last copy to the section "Works on Khwarezm Turkic" and states that it is in Khwarezm Turkic. As the reason, he points to facts such as the substitutions of *y>d* (interdental) in Turkic words in the work, preservation of *g* in cases of dropping in words with more than one syllable. At the same time, he notes that examples with *d* in the dictionary belong to Oghuz languages. But there are more examples with *f* [See: 7, p. 385].

Since Ercilasun's interpretation, which he did not substantiate with examples, does not create a clear picture, we should note that, as mentioned above, Ibn Muhanna used Turkestan Turkic. So, suffix *-din* (دين) of the ablative case, suffixes *-qa*, *-ka* (قا، ك) of the dative case of the noun, suffixes *-ğan* (غان) + *-li* (لي) (*gəlgəli* "comer", *barğali* "walker") that form adjectivized participle, suffixes *-ğay*, *gay* [18, p. 117] of the future tense in the 14th chapter are characteristics of Karakhanid Turkic. These examples are given in the same version in European and Istanbul copies. Some of the above-mentioned suffixes are even attributed to "the Turks of our country" by Ibn Muhanna. For example, the suffixes *-ğay*, *-gay*, which indicates the future tense of the verb: *vuruşğay biz* (وَرُشْغای بیز) "biz vuruşacağiq" (*trans.*: we will fight), *dutuşğay biz* (دُتُشْغای بیز) "biz tutaşacağiq" (*trans.*: we will scrap), *nə bolğay?* (نە بولغای) "nə olacaq?" (*trans.*: what will happen?). It should be noted that the suffix *-ğay* also existed in the Kipchak language in the 13th-14th centuries. You can see it in Abu Hayyan's dictionary and "Codex Kumanikus". If we take into account that our language has Oghuz-Kipchak characteristics, and Ibn Muhanna's note "The Turks of our country sometimes say *nə olğay?* instead of *nə bolğay?*" [18, p. 80] shows the presence of this suffix in Azerbaijani Turkic language in the 13th-14th centuries. So, it is possible to observe verbs with the suffix *-ğay* in Ghazi Burhanuddin's language, a representative of the 14th century:

Cənnətdə yüzün kibi *hur olmağay*,

Məst gözün kibi *məstur olmağay* [9, 694th tuyug]

In our opinion, the language of Nematullah Kishwari, who lived in the territory of South Azerbaijan in the middle of the 15th century, is closer to the dialect of the local Turks, which are mentioned in Ibn Muhanna's dictionary. Because although we cannot see the suffix *-ğay* in the language of Nasimi who lived in the 14th-15th century, we can see this suffix in the poems by Kishwari who lived in the middle and second half of the 15th century:

Həlqəyi-zülfünü görgəc könlümün əfğanıdır,

Tifyanlıq kim, *çığırğay* nəgəhan yılan görüb [14, p.17]

Perhaps the presence of this suffix in Kishwari's work is associated with Navai's influence. Indeed, Alishir Navai, who was a prominent representative of medieval tasawwuf literature and rendered invaluable services in the popularization of Turkic poetry, influenced greatly the works of 15th century Azerbaijani poets, including Nematullah Kishwari. But it should be taken into account that this suffix is also observed in the language of Ghazi Burhanuddin, a representative of the 14th century. Moreover, this is the fact that the suffix *-ğay* is presented as the only future tense morpheme in the 13th century southern Azerbaijani dialect, which is described in Ibn Muhanna's dictionary.

Gyzylgul Abdullayeva points out that the tasks and functions of the morpheme *-ğay//gəy* coincide with suffix *-acaq²* of the future definite tense, and that it could no longer find a wide scope in the language of representatives of the literature of the 17th century, and notes that this morpheme was used a lot in Muhammad Amani's language [1, p. 118].

According to Mirza Rahimov, the suffix *-ğay* means desire, intention, goal [16, p.44]. İlkin Gulsoy also shows that this morpheme is a optative form of the verb with the suffix *-a*, *-ə* in the modern Azerbaijani language, and based on the opinions of Turkologists, he defines the way of its development as following: *-ğay>-ay>-a//ə* [10, p.76].

It should be noted that suffixes neither *-acaq²*, nor *-ar²*, and *-ır⁴* of future tense are observed in Ibn Muhanna's dictionary. The lexicographer shows only the morpheme *-ğay* as a future tense suffix. Melioransky points out that in the dictionary there are the forms of this suffix *-ğay* (غای), *-kay* (کای), *-gay* (غای), and even the parallels *-ğa* (غاء), *-ka* (كاء), which underwent sound dropping [13, p. LXXII-LXXIII].

It should be noted for comparison that the suffix *-ır⁴* was used in verbs to form the future tense in the "Dada Gorgud" epos. The suffix *-acaq²* was used only with the auxiliary verb "olmaq" (*trans.*: to be) (*çıqaracaq olanca*, *açılacaq olursa*, *basılacaq olursam*, *qurtaracaq olursa*, etc.) and adjectivized participle (*varacaq yer*, *yatacaq yer*, *yıqılacaq ev*, etc.), because it seems to be experiencing a new stage of creation and development [5, D98, D51, D118, D192].

Suffix *-acaq/-əcək* of the future definite tense is not observed in Ghazi Burhanuddin's language. Instead, the suffix *-isar*, *-isər*, which functioned as a complete grammatical synonym of this suffix, was functional for the language of the 13th-14th centuries, and was noticeably limited in the 15th century, is observed in the language of the poet. Suffixes *-ar*, *-ər* of the future definite tense are widely used in Ghazi Burhanuddin's language. For example:

Gəzəriüz dərbədən eşqün için biz,

Ümmana girürüz Ceyhun için biz [9, p.109]

We can see the suffix *-acaq²* in the adjectivized participle and participle in the language of Nasimin, who lived and created about 100 years after Ibn Muhanna. For example, as the adjectivized participle:

Zey – *Zaval* irmiyə bu din mülkünə,

Rey – *Rəfiq olmayacaq* şeytana mən;

As participle:

Bilsəm bu meyi haram edən kim,

Fitva bulacaq halal olurmu?

Nasimi used the suffix *-isar²* (*Ol gündə həşr olisər*, *ol gündə macəradır*) for future definite tense and *-ar²* (*Zülfü qaşukirpigin gördükə adam məst olar* / *Fitnələr çün kim qopar*, *ol surəti-Həvvayı gör*) for the indefinite future tense to express the future tense as Ghazi Burhanuddin.

Also worth noting is that the suffixes *-dıq*, *-dik*, which are the first person plural of the past tense verb in the Turkic languages, were translated by Ibn Muhanna as the third person singular, for example: he translated the word *görmədik* (چورمديک) (*trans.*: we didn't see) as "görmədi" (بيلمديک) (*trans.*: he didn't see) and the word *bilmədik* (*trans.*: we didn't know) as "bilmədi" (*trans.*: he didn't know) [18, p. 135]. Melioransky suggested the possibility of a mistake here [13, p. 38]. Mahmud Kashgari showed that instead of the suffix *-di*, *-di* (دی), the Oguz used the suffixes *-duq* (دُق) in words as *qaf-lı* (ق) and *-dik* (دِک) in words as *ğayn-lı* (غ), and gave examples:

Ya qurduq (يا فُرْدُق) – *O, yay qurdu*;
Mən ya qurduq (من يا فُرْدُق) – *Mən yay qurdum*;
Biz ya qurduq (بِز يا فُرْدُق) – *Biz yay qurduq*;
Olar tağqağduq (الَار تاغقا اَغْدُق) – *Onlar dağ*
çıxdılar [11, p.78; 19, p. 51]

B.Chobanzade, who conducted an in-depth study of the suffixes *-duq* (دُق), *-dük* (دُك), wrote: “The existence of the forms *mən getmədik* (*trans.*: I didn’t go) (من كتمدك) and *sən getmədik* (*trans.*: you didn’t go) (سن كتمدك) in Turkic systematic languages show that they are not relevant not only in terms of quantity (singular and plural), but also in terms of person. We still observ it today in gerundial constructions and forms, for example: *biz getdikdə* (*trans.*: when we go), *mən getdikdə* (*trans.*: when I go), *o getdikdə* (*trans.*: when he goes), etc.” [4, p. 85].

The suffix *-qa* (*tağqa* – to the mountain) of dative case, which was concerned the Oghuz by Kashgari, in abovementioned example “*Olar tağqa ağduq*” (الَار تاغقا اَغْدُق) (*trans.*: they climbed the mountain) was widely used in Ibn Muhanna’s language.

The form of suffix *-ğa* of the dative case and suffix *-ni* of the accusative case in the works by Imadaddin Nasimi, who lived at the end of the 14th century and the beginning of the 15th century, are reflected in the following verse.

Yaman yaxşı ilə yaxşı müdara eyləsə, yaxşı,
 Kişi yetməz muradınğa, bülənd
 dutmazsahümmətini.

These suffixes are observed in the grammar section of Abu Hayya’s “*Kitab al-idrak al-lisan al-atrak*” dictionary. As we know, he compiled a dictionary of Egyptian Kipchak language and gave an explanation on the grammatical features of the Kipchak dialect. Abu Hayyan explained in detail the points of adding the suffixes *-ğa*, *-kə* of the dative case and the suffix *-in* of accusative case to the root of the words ending with a consonant [3, p. 97]. For this reason, the suffixes shown in ancient Azerbaijani Turkic language with Oghuz-Kipchak characteristics is normal and cannot be considered Jagatai elements at all.

Unfortunately, it should be noted that the abovementioned tense suffixes are not observed in Hadi Mirzazadeh’s “*Historical Grammar of the Azerbaijani Language*”. He even considered *-ğa*, *-gə* forms of the dative case to be the influence of other ancient Turkic peoples [15, p. 43].

But, we can see the signs of the phonetic variants of nasal *-ğa* // *-gə* // *-qa* // *-ka* of the ancient dative case suffix in Turkic languages in the pronunciation of the personal pronouns *mən* (*trans.*: I), *sən* (*trans.*: you) as *manqa*, *sanqa* in the dative case in the Zangilan and Gazakh dialects of modern Azerbaijan. Here, *-ng* was formed as a result of the combination of the dative case suffix *-n* (ن) + *-qa* (قا). According to A. Demirchizade, “... as a result of development through sound refinement, the nasal *-q* and *-k*, which was used in our

language since ancient times, later became the voiceless *nun* (ن), and the deaf *nun* gradually merged with the consonant “*n*”. Indeed, as confirmed by the facts in individual dialects, the development path of *nq/ng* → *n* → *n* is clearly observed here” [6, p. 39].

Conclusion

We confirm Chobanzadeh’s opinion and believe that the Istanbul copy is a manuscript that mostly reflects Azerbaijani Turkic language. It is possible to observe the following peculiarities specific to our language in Ibn Muhanna’s dictionary:

1) The analysis of the orthography in Ibn Muhanna’s dictionary shows that extensions are applied at the end of Turkic words in the orthography of the Arabic alphabet. For example, *qılıc* (*trans.*: sword) (قَلِيج), *qərintaş* (*trans.*: sibling) (قَرِنْتاش), *kişi* (*trans.*: man) (كِشِي), etc. This stress falls on the last syllable of the word.

2) Melioransky noted that unlike Turkestan Turkic, words in Azerbaijani Turkic end with voiced consonants [13, p. XXXVII]. For example, *atmaq* (*trans.*: throw) (اَطْمَق), *barmaq* (*trans.*: finger) (بَارْمَاق), *qılıc* (*trans.*: sword) (قَلِيج), etc. It is also mentioned in the dictionary that the word ending with a voiced consonant takes a voiced consonant suffix, e.g., *sançdı* (*trans.*: he thrust) (سَانْجَدِي), *İraqdan* (*trans.*: from Iraq) (عِرَاق دِن). The word *qılıc* (*trans.*: sword), which means “*qılinc*” (*trans.*: sword), is given with the deaf consonant *ç* [13, p. 0106] in the European copies, and with the voiced consonant *c* (قَلِيج) [18, p.81] in the Istanbul copy. As a continuation of the theme of voiced consonants, Ibn Muhanna attributed the *z* sound to Azerbaijani Turkic language and the *s* sound to Turkestan Turkic in *z* > *s* change. For example, *yaramaz*– *yaramas* (*trans.*: naughty), *kəlməz* – *kələməs* (*trans.*: old) [18, p. 80].

3) The *q* (ق) in the middle of words in other Turkic dialects has widely changed to *x* (خ) in Azerbaijani Turkic. Ibn Muhanna wrote a special explanation about this and gives examples: *toxli* (توخلی) – *toqli* (توقلی) (*trans.*: sheep), *səxtadı* – *səqtadı* (*trans.*: false), etc. [18, p. 8].

4) Ibn Muhanna showed that “the Turks of our country” said *nə oldı? nə olğay?* instead of *nə buldı?, nə bulğay?* (*trans.*: what will happen?). According to Melioransky, the auxiliary verb *olmaq* (*trans.*: to be), which is formed as a result of the dropping of the *b* sound, is a peculiar characteristic only of the Southern Turkic dialects. According to Bekir Chobanzadeh, the contrast between *bol* and *ol* started in the 14th century and first observed in various word combinations within a sentence [4, p. 81].

5) The transition *ç* > *ş* ([ch]>[sh]), *c* > *ş* ([j]>[sh]) is a peculiar characteristic of Azerbaijani dialects. Ibn Muhanna emphasized that the *c* sound is pronounced similar to *ş* in the language of the local Turks.

In Istanbul copy	According to Melioransky
<i>Aştı, actı</i> (أَشْتِي، أَجْتِي)	<i>Actı, açtı, aştı</i> (أَشْتِي، أَجْتِي، أَشْتِي)
<i>qacdı</i> (قَجْدِي)	<i>qaştı</i> (قَاشْتِي)
<i>bişdi</i> (بِيَشْدِي)	<i>biçdi</i> (بِيَجْدِي)
<i>aşmaq, acmaq</i> (أَشْمَق، أَجْمَق)	<i>açmaq</i> (أَجْمَق)

6) Dropping of the consonant *y* at the beginning of the word. Məsələn, üzüm (اوزوم), *ir/ır* (اير) “melody, song”. This phonetic event is not widely reflected in Ibn Muhanna’s dictionary. Because the dropping of the *y* sound in the medieval South Azerbaijani dialect was not yet sufficiently developed. This can be observed in the poems by Ghazi Burhanuddin in the 14th century and Kishvari in the 15th century. Gyzylgul Abdullayeva showed that words beginning with *y* have a wider scope and prevailed in terms of use frequency in the phonetics of the 17th century Azerbaijani literary language [1, p. 135].

7) *-durur* predicate suffix [18, p. 94: Bu kimindurur? (بو کیم ینک درور)] is observed in ancient Azerbaijani and Anatolian Turkic. “It is used as *-turur* in Koptürk, Uyghur, Karakhanid, Khwarezm, Jagatai and Kipchak Turkic languages” [17, p. 165].

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